

THERMAL BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF VARIABLE ANGLE TOW COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Assumed that the fibre angle of each ply varies linearly along the length of the laminate, the governing equation of the thermal buckling problem is derived based on the classical plate theory. By expressing the out of plane displacement as the Chebyshev polynomials and characteristic functions, the critical thermal buckling loads of laminate plates with variable angle tows(VAT) under different boundary conditions and uniform temperature rise are solved by employing Rayleigh-Ritz method. Results are compared with those existed in references and the accuracy of the solutions obtained in this paper is validated. Moreover, the effect of fibre paths and boundary conditions on the critical thermal buckling loads is discussed in numerical examples. It is found that the critical thermal buckling loads of variable angle tow laminate plates can be improved by selecting proper fibre paths. The numerical results show the critical thermal buckling loads of VAT plate considered here can provide a 5.76%, 6.02%, 19.21% and 13.43% promotion compared with the traditional plate with linear fibers under boundary conditions of SSSS, CSCS, SCSC and CCCC, respectively. And the results obtained here can provide a reference for the design of this new kind of variable stiffness structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of advanced fiber placement machines, the forming of variable angle tow composite materials becomes possible. The fiber angle changing with position over the entire plane results in varying in-plane stiffness properties in a ply which providing more potential to design and manufacture composite laminate plates. Accordingly, the usage of this kind of new composite materials in aerospace engineering has significantly increased in the last decade. Previous studies have shown that variable angle tow composite materials possess higher mechanical performance than the traditional composite materials reinforced by linear fibers. Some progresses in the buckling, failure and vibration of variable angle tow laminate plates are reviewed by Ribeiro[1].

The buckling problems of variable angle tow composite plates have attracted much attention and a number of work[2-7] has extensively proved that variable angle tow composite materials have more significant improvement of buckling load. A pioneering work on the buckling problem of the variable angle tow composite laminate plates has taken by Hyer and his coworkers[2, 3]. They obtained the optimal curved fiber path for the maximum of the buckling critical loads by using the finite element method and experimentally verified the evident promotion for buckling load in contrasted to traditional plate. Gürdal et al.[8] investigated the in-plane and buckling responses of variable stiffness panels by assuming that the fiber orientation angle of the individual layers has a unidirectional variation based on a linear function. And numerical results indicated that a much high improvement of the buckling load can be obtained by varying the stiffness perpendicular to the loading. Wu et al.[9, 10] used Rayleigh-Ritz method to determine the prebuckling loads distributions and critical buckling load of variable angle tow plates and they proposed an optimization strategy for the design of postbuckling behavior of VAT composite laminates under axial compression. Raju et al.[11, 12] employed Differential Quadrature Method to the prebuckling and postbuckling analysis of variable

angle tow plates. And the results show that variable angle tow plates have great superiority compared with the traditional composite plates reinforced by linear fibers. Langley[13] used the finite element method to perform structural analysis and obtain the optimal in-plane stiffness and buckling load for variable stiffness plate. Weaver et al.[14] experimentally investigated the difference of variable angle tow composite plates and traditional composite plates and the results show that variable angle tow composite plates have apparently lower in-plane displacement and 30% higher buckling load.

During the operational life, the laminate composition plates often suffer vast thermal environment change especially in aircrafts and space systems and thermal buckling analysis is greatly essential to utilizing the composite laminates. Thermal buckling problem of traditional composite laminate plates with linear fibers has been widely researched in the last decades. Whitney and Ashto[15] used classical laminate plate theory to investigate the bending, buckling and vibration problem of traditional composite plate under hygrothermal environment. Sneed and Palazotto[16] studied the the hygrothermal effects on the buckling problem of composite laminate cylindrical shell. Kant et al.[17] studied the critical thermal in the buckling problem of skew fibre-reinforced composite laminate plate under different boundary conditions by using shear deformable finite element models. Matsunaga[18] investigated thermal buckling of cross-ply laminated composite and sandwich plates according to a two-dimensional global higher-order deformation theory. Shiau et al.[19] investigated the thermal buckling behaviors of composite laminate plates by using finite element method and detailly investigated the effects of various ratios, aspect ratios, fiber angle, stacking sequence and boundary conditions.

However, up to now, the literature on the thermal buckling problem of variable angle tow composite plates is rare. Wu et al.[20] experimentally investigated the thermal properties of variable angle tow composite plates. Abdalla et al.[21] obtained thermomechanical response for variable angle tow laminates under uniform end shorting and thermal effects. Duran et al.[22] obtain the thermal critical buckling temperatures for variable angle tow laminates based on classical lamination theory and the finite element method. The results show that the curved fiber path configurations can provide a 36.9% increase of resistance to thermal buckling in comparison to straight fiber configurations.

In view of the importance of the thermal buckling problem of the new variable angle tow laminates, it is necessary to further study this problem. Therefore, we investigate the critical thermal buckling loads of variable angle tow plates under different boundary conditions and uniform temperature rise by using Rayleigh-Ritz method in this paper.

2 DEFINITION OF THE FIBER REFERENCE PATH

Considering a rectangular plate with length a , width b and thickness h , shown in Fig.1, the fiber reference paths vary linearly along the length which can be written as follows with respect to normalized coordinates

$$\theta(\xi) = \begin{cases} (\theta_1 - \theta_0)\xi + \theta_0, & 0 \leq \xi \leq 1 \\ (\theta_0 - \theta_1)\xi + \theta_0, & -1 \leq \xi \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where θ_1 and θ_0 , respectively represent the fiber orientation angle at the end and at the center of the plate in a ply. And $\xi = 2x/a$.

Figure 1: One ply of composite laminates with variable angle tows($\theta_1 = 20^\circ$ and $\theta_0 = 60^\circ$)

3 THEORETICAL MODEL

According to the classical lamination plate theory (CLPT), the displacement field of a thin laminate can be written as

$$u = u_0 - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x}, \quad v = v_0 - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y}, \quad w = w_0 \quad (2)$$

where u and v represent in-plane displacement of plate respectively and w stands for out-plane displacement of plate. And u_0 , v_0 and w_0 , respectively, denote displacement of mid-plane of the plate.

The corresponding strain field of the plate can be defined as follows

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} - z \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2}, \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} - z \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2}, \quad \gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} - 2z \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (3)$$

Including thermal effects, the constitutive relations of a thin laminate can be written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon^{(0)} \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} N^T \\ M^T \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where N and M are the stress resultant forces and moments and N^T and M^T are thermal stress resultants and thermal moment resultants caused by uniform temperature change. A , B and D represent the in-plane stiffness matrix, coupling matrix and bending stiffness matrix respectively. $\varepsilon^{(0)}$ and κ are mid-plane strain and mid-plane curvature.

For constant uniform temperature change ΔT and laminate plates which the material properties and geometric shape of the laminate plate is symmetric with respect to the mid-plane, the coupling matrix and thermal moment resultants of the laminates vanish, the constitutive relations can be simplified as follows

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon^{(0)} \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} N^T \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The matrixes appeared in Equation (5) can be written as

$$\varepsilon^{(0)} = \left\{ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right\}^T, \quad \kappa = \left\{ -\frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2}, -\frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2}, -2\frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \right\}^T \quad (6)$$

$$N^T = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} [\bar{Q}]_k [\alpha]_k \Delta T dz \quad (7)$$

$$\{A, D\} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} [\bar{Q}]_k \{1, z^2\} dz = \sum_{k=1}^n [\bar{Q}]_k \left\{ z_k - z_{k-1}, \frac{z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3}{3} \right\} \quad (8)$$

where $[\alpha]_k$ represents coefficients of thermal expansion along x and y directions of the k^{th} layer of the VAT plate. $[\bar{Q}]_k$ represents reduced transformed stiffness matrix of the k^{th} layer of the VAT plate which can be written by elastic constants for engineering.

$$\begin{aligned} [\bar{Q}_{11}]_k &= U_1 + U_2 \cos(2\theta_k(x)) + U_3 \cos(4\theta_k(x)) \\ [\bar{Q}_{12}]_k &= U_4 - U_3 \cos(4\theta_k(x)) \\ [\bar{Q}_{22}]_k &= U_1 - U_2 \cos(2\theta_k(x)) + U_3 \cos(4\theta_k(x)) \\ [\bar{Q}_{66}]_k &= U_5 - U_3 \cos(4\theta_k(x)) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where U_i are constant values and can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= \frac{1}{8}(3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}), U_2 = \frac{1}{2}(Q_{11} - Q_{22}) \\ U_3 &= \frac{1}{8}(Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}), U_4 = \frac{1}{8}(Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}) \\ U_5 &= \frac{1}{8}(Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where Q_{ij} can be written by elastic constants for engineering as follows

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, Q_{66} = G_{12} \quad (11)$$

For the considered boundary conditions, the pre-buckling analysis can be easily obtained by using classical laminate plate theory. In this work, the in-plane boundary stresses are zero and four edges of the plate cannot be moved which means the in-plane displacements are zero at four edges. In other words, the symmetrically variable angle tow plate is only subjected to constant uniform thermal loads ΔT in which the pre-buckling loads can be easily obtained according to Equation (8) and written as

$$\{N^p\} = \{-N^T\} = - \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} [\bar{Q}]_k [\alpha]_k \Delta T dz \quad (12)$$

where $\{N^p\}$ represents pre-buckling loads of the VAT plate.

4 Thermal Buckling

The total potential energy can be obtained by

$$\Pi = U + V \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2b}{a^3} D_{11}(\xi, \eta) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} \right)^2 + \frac{2a}{b^3} D_{22}(\xi, \eta) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \eta^2} \right)^2 + \frac{4}{ab} D_{12}(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \eta^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{8}{ab} D_{66}(\xi, \eta) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} \right)^2 + \frac{8}{a^2} D_{16}(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + \frac{8}{b^2} D_{26}(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \eta^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} \right] d\xi d\eta \end{aligned}$$

$$V = \lambda \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left[N_x^p \frac{b}{2a} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \xi} \right)^2 + N_y^p \frac{a}{2b} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 + N_{xy}^p \frac{\partial w}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \eta} \right] d\xi d\eta$$

where λ represents load multiplier to determine thermal buckling load. And $\eta = 2y/b$

The out of plane displacement w of the VAT plate can be expressed as[23, 24]

$$w = \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{n=0}^N A_{mn} X_m(\xi) Y_n(\eta) = F_w(\xi, \eta) \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{n=0}^N A_{mn} P_m(\xi) P_n(\eta) \quad (14)$$

where m and n are the truncation orders of the Chebyshev polynomial series, A_{mn} is the coefficients to be determined, $P_i(\mu)$ ($i=1, 2, 3, \dots; \mu = \xi, \eta$) is one dimensional i th Chebyshev polynomial which is

$$P_i(\mu) = \cos[(i-1)\arccos(\mu)] \quad (15)$$

$F_w(\xi, \eta)$ is defined as boundary characteristic function which is determined by the boundary conditions and geometric shape of the laminate plate. For a rectangular plate, the boundary characteristic function can be easily written as follows

$$F_w(\xi, \eta) = (1-\xi)^l (1+\xi)^l (1-\eta)^l (1+\eta)^l \quad (16)$$

where l is associated with the boundary conditions which $l=0, 1, 2$ correspond to free, simply supported and clamped boundary respectively in this work.

Applying the principle of minimum potential energy

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial A_{mn}} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Then we can obtain the critical buckling load through solving the $(M+1) \times (N+1)$ eigenvalue problem in Equation (17)

$$\{K_M + \lambda K_T\} \{A\} = 0 \quad (19)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} K_M = & \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{4b}{a^3} D_{11}(\xi, \eta) X_m^{(2)} Y_n X_k^{(2)} Y_l + \frac{4a}{b^3} D_{22}(\xi, \eta) X_m Y_n^{(2)} X_k Y_l^{(2)} \right. \\ & + \frac{4}{ab} D_{12}(\xi, \eta) (X_m^{(2)} Y_n X_k Y_l^{(2)} + X_m Y_n^{(2)} X_k^{(2)} Y_l) + \frac{16}{ab} D_{66}(\xi, \eta) X_m^{(1)} Y_n^{(1)} X_k^{(1)} Y_l^{(1)} \\ & + \frac{8}{a^2} D_{16}(\xi, \eta) (X_m^{(2)} Y_n X_k^{(1)} Y_l^{(1)} + X_m^{(1)} Y_n^{(1)} X_k^{(2)} Y_l) \\ & \left. + \frac{8}{b^2} D_{26}(\xi, \eta) (X_m Y_n^{(2)} X_k^{(1)} Y_l^{(1)} + X_m^{(1)} Y_n^{(1)} X_k Y_l^{(2)}) \right] d\xi d\eta \\ K_T = & \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left[N_x^T \frac{b}{a} X_m^{(1)} Y_n X_k^{(1)} Y_l + N_y^T \frac{a}{b} X_m Y_n^{(1)} X_k Y_l^{(1)} \right. \\ & \left. + N_{xy}^T (X_m Y_n^{(1)} X_k^{(1)} Y_l + X_m^{(1)} Y_n X_k Y_l^{(1)}) \right] d\xi d\eta \end{aligned}$$

K_M represents bending stiffness matrix and K_T is the matrix describing the in-plane stress field caused by uniform temperature change. The critical buckling temperature ΔT_{cr} of the variable angle tow plate can be obtained by applying

$$\Delta T_{cr} = \lambda_s \Delta T \quad (20)$$

where λ_s denotes the smallest eigenvalue of Eq.(19).

5 NUMERICAL MODELS AND RESULTS

In this part, the critical buckling loads found in work of Duran are taken as reference. The material properties are shown in Table 1. And the material geometric parameters are given as $a = b = 0.15m$, $h = 0.001016m$ and $n = 4$.

Engineering constant	E_1 /GPa	E_2 /GPa	ν_{12}	G_{12} /GPa	ρ_1 /C ⁻¹	ρ_2 /C ⁻¹
Duran[21]	155	8.07	0.22	4.55	-0.07	30.1

Table 1: Material properties in the numerical models

5.1 Validation and Convergence Study

Convergence study is performed in this part and Datas in Table 2 and Table 3 expressed that the proposed method in this paper has a good convergence and perfect accuracy in calculating critical thermal buckling load under different boundary conditions.

$M \times N$	3×3	4×4	5×5	6×6	7×7	8×8	Duran[20]
$[0 \pm \langle 60.7^\square 32.19^\square \rangle]_s$	36.29	35.15	35.06	34.74	34.69	34.57	34.26
Difference	5.9%	2.5%	2.3%	1.4%	1.2%	0.9%	-

Table 2: Thermal buckling loads for simply supported square plates

Table 2 shows that compared with Duran’s work which used FEM to investigate the VAT thermal buckling problem, the Chebyshev-Ritz method proposed in this paper perform good convergence and accuracy in calculating critical thermal buckling load with simply supported boundary conditions for variable angle tow laminate plate.

5.2 Effects of fiber paths and boundary conditions

The effects of fiber paths and boundary conditions are discussed and the results are collected in Fig. 2 which express that the thermal buckling loads are closely connected with fiber paths and boundary conditions. Moreover, according to numerical results, $[0 \pm \langle 60^\square | 30^\square \rangle]_s$ VAT plate which thermal buckling load is 34.68, can provide a 5.76%, 6.02%, 19.21% and 13.43% promotion compared with $[\pm 45^\square]_s$ traditional plate which represented by dash line in Figure 1 under SSSS, CSCS, SCSC and CCCC boundary conditions respectively.

Figure 2: Critical thermal loads of VAT plate with different fiber paths
(Case A-SSSS, Case B-CSCS, Case C-SCSC, Case D-CCCC).

Fig. 2 shows the critical temperature loads of variable angle tow laminates with different fiber paths $[0 \pm \langle \theta_0 | \theta_1 \rangle]_s$ for different boundary conditions. A family of curves corresponding to various values of θ_1 for a given value of θ_0 under different boundary conditions are labeled in the Fig. 2. The Dash lines across Fig. 2 represent the straight-fiber laminates where value of θ_1 is equal to θ_0 as 45° . The fiber paths for the maximum critical temperature loads can be obtained from Fig. 2. It is seen that the value of critical temperature loads strongly depend on the fiber paths and boundary conditions. When the fiber paths are same for example $[0 \pm \langle 60^\circ | 0^\circ \rangle]_s$ variable angle tow plates, the critical temperature loads are higher than straight-fiber laminate plates for CSCS and CCCC boundary conditions and are lower for SSSS and SCSC boundary conditions. While the critical temperature loads for $[0 \pm \langle 60^\circ | 30^\circ \rangle]_s$ variable angle tow plates are always above the straight-fiber laminate plates. It is also observed that not all kinds of variable angle tow laminate plates have greater thermal buckling loads than traditional laminate plates. Only selecting proper fiber paths which points above the dash line in Figure 2 can more greatly elevate the critical thermal buckling loads and enhance the mechanical performance.

Figure 3: Critical thermal loads of VAT plate under different boundary conditions

(Case A- $\theta_0 = 90^\circ$, Case B- $\theta_0 = 60^\circ$, Case C- $\theta_0 = 30^\circ$, Case D- $\theta_0 = 0^\circ$).

Fig. 3 shows the variation trend of critical thermal loads with respect to θ_1 for different boundary conditions. From Fig.3, it is worth noting that no matter what kinds of the fiber paths, the critical thermal buckling loads of CCCC laminate plate are always highest while the critical thermal buckling loads of SSSS laminate plate are always lowest among the considered four boundary conditions. It is also observed that the higher critical thermal buckling loads between CSCS and SCSC boundary conditions strongly depend on the fiber paths. It is seen that the critical thermal buckling loads curves of CSCS and SCSC have intersection point in Case B and Case C. And as the value of θ_0 decrease, value of θ_1 at the intersection point increase.

5.3 Effects of ratio of width to thickness

Figure 4: Critical thermal loads of VAT plate under different boundary conditions with variable ratio of width to thickness.

Fig. 4 shows the critical thermal buckling loads for $\left[0 \pm \left\langle 60^\circ \right| 30^\circ \right]_s$ VAT plates vs the width to thickness for different boundary conditions. It is seen that the critical thermal buckling loads are also closely related with the ratio of width to thickness. The critical thermal buckling loads monotonically decrease under all considered boundary conditions as the ratio of width to thickness increase. No matter what boundary conditions are, when the ratio of width to thickness is less than 200, the reducing rates of critical thermal buckling load are very steep. However, when the ratio of width to thickness is more than 400, the reducing rates becomes more and more gentle and the differences of thermal buckling loads for different boundary conditions are more and more small which means that boundary conditions have little effects on the critical thermal buckling loads at that moment.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The numerical results show that the critical thermal buckling loads are closely related with fiber paths and boundary conditions. The critical thermal buckling loads of CCCC laminate plate are always highest while the critical thermal buckling loads of SSSS laminate plate are always lowest among the considered four boundary conditions. The numerical results shows VAT plate considered here can provide a 5.76%, 6.02%, 19.21% and 13.43% promotion compared with traditional plate under SSSS, CSCS, SCSC and CCCC boundary conditions respectively. It is worth noting that not all variable angle tow laminate plates have greater thermal buckling loads than traditional laminate plates which means only selecting proper fiber paths can more greatly elevate the critical thermal buckling loads and enhance the mechanical performance.

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